

The Abdus Salam
**International Centre
for Theoretical Physics**

12th AAMP Meeting & EFOMP School

Description:

We are pleased to announce that the Italian Association of Medical Physicists (AIFM) will host the 12th Alpe Adria Medical Physics Meeting, to be held from 22 to 24 May 2024 at the Abdus Salam International Centre for Theoretical Physics (ICTP). The meeting is organised in cooperation with the Medical Physics Societies of Austria, Croatia, Hungary, North Macedonia, Serbia and Slovenia. A pre-meeting EFOMP School on New Technologies in Radiotherapy will be held on 21-22 May, free of admission for participants of the Alpe Adria meeting.

EFOMP "School on Advanced Radiotherapy Technology" (21-22 May 2025):

New technologies in Medical Physics: FLASH, SFRT, Radionuclide Therapy and SBRT

SPEAKERS:

Eeva Boeman – Department of Oncology, Tampere University Hospital, Finland
Marco Esposito – ICTP, Abdus Salam International Centre for Theoretical Physics, Trieste, Italy
Francesco Romano – Istituto Nazionale di Fisica Nucleare (INFN), Catania, Italy
Joao Seco – DKFZ, German Cancer Research Center, Heidelberg, Germany
Lidia Strigari – IRCCS Azienda Ospedaliero-Universitaria di Bologna (University Hospital of Bologna), Bologna, Italy

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC COMMITTEE:

Austria: Peter Kuess, Uwe Wolff, Brigitte Zurl
Croatia: Dea Dundara Debeljuh, Slaven Jurković, Ivana Kralik
Italy: Paola Bregant, Luca Brombal, Marco Esposito
Hungary: Tibor Major, Csilla Pesznyak, Tamas Poczsa
North Macedonia: Dushko Lukarski, Tomislav Stankovski
Serbia: Borislava Petrovic, Jelena Samac, Milana Vezirovic
Slovenia: Bozidar Casar, Manca Podvratnik, Petra Tomše

REGISTRATION FEE:

Early: Until March 15th, 2025

Student/Resident	Member*	Non-Member
70€	150€	200€

Late: Until May 15th, 2025

Student/Resident	Member*	Non-Member
100€	200€	250€

*AIFM, AMPBE, CROMPA, HSMP, ÖGMP, SAMP, SBS, UMFUBIH

21 - 24 May 2025

Trieste, Italy

Application and Deadlines:

For applicants requesting financial and/or visa support:

15 February 2025

For all other applicants:
15 March 2025

DIRECTORS:

P. Bregant, ASUGI - University Hospital, Italy
L. Brombai, University of Trieste, Italy
R. Longo, University of Trieste and INFN, Italy
R. Padovani, ICTP, Italy
M. Severgnini, ASUGI - University Hospital, Italy

LOCAL ORGANIZER:

M. Esposito, ICTP, Italy

FURTHER INFORMATION:

E-mail: smr4071@ictp.it

Web: <https://indico.ictp.it/event/10836/>

Female scientists are encouraged to apply.

12th AAMP Meeting & EFOMP School | (smr 4071)

Wednesday, 21 May 2025

14:00 - 18:00 EFOMP School

14:00 **Registration 20'**

Upon arrival, Visitors not staying in the ICTP Guest Houses, are kindly requested to complete registration formalities at the Leonardo Building (Lobby) from 14.00 to 14.20.

14:20 **Introduction to the EFOMP school 10'**

Speaker: Seco JOAO (Heidelberg University and DKFZ, Germany)

Material: **Video**

14:30 **Introduction to new technologies in Medical Physics: FLASH, SFRT and molecular therapy 1h0'**

Speaker: Seco JOAO (Heidelberg University and DKFZ, Germany)

Material: **Video**

15:30 **Molecular therapy (alpha and beta radionuclide therapy) 1h0'**

Speaker: Lidia STRIGARI (IRCCS Azienda Ospedaliero-Universitaria di Bologna Department of Medical Physics, Italy)

Material: **Video**

16:30 **Coffee Break 30'**

17:00 **Stereotactic Body Radiation Therapy (SBRT) for FLASH 1h0'**

Speaker: Seco JOAO (Heidelberg University and DKFZ, Germany)

Material: **Video**

Thursday, 22 May 2025

09:00 - 15:00 EFOMP School

09:00 **SBRT techniques and applications to clinical cases 1h0'**

Speaker: Eva BOMAN (EFOMP, Finland)

Material: **Video**

10:00 **In vivo dosimetry for SBRT 1h0'**

Speaker: Marco ESPOSITO (ICTP, Italy)

Material: **Video**

11:00 **Coffee Break 30'**

11:30 **Technological challenges and novel dosimetry methods for FLASH Radiotherapy 1h0'**

Speaker: Francesco ROMANO (INFN Catania Division, Italy)

Material: **Video**

12:30 **Lunch Break 2h0'**

14:30 - 14:45

AAPM Meeting

Chair: Renato PADOVANI (ICTP, Italy), Peter KUESS (Department of Radiation Oncology, Medical University Vienna, Austria)

14:30 **Opening Remarks 15'**

Speaker: Sandro SCANDOLO (ICTP, Italy), Carlo CAVEDON (AIFM)

14:45 - 15:25

AI

14:45 **Investigation of Biases in AI-based Models for Radiation Oncology 10'**

Speaker: Peter KUESS (Department of Radiation Oncology, Medical University Vienna, Austria)

14:55 **Towards optimized prescription metrics in novel radiotherapy techniques: A Machine Learning-guided study. 10'**

Speaker: Alfredo FERNANDEZ-RODRIGUEZ (Institute Curie, Paris-Saclay University, Centre national de la recherche scientifique, France)

15:05 **AI-Enhanced PET/CT Imaging: Transforming Oncology Diagnosis and Treatment Planning 10'**

Speaker: Subhash KHERUKA (Sultan Qaboos Comprehensive Cancer Care, and Research Center (University Medical City), Muscat, Oman)

15:15 **The need for standardization of geometrical feature computation for dose prevision models in radiotherapy 10'**

Speaker: Farah BEN HAMMOUDA (ICTP, Italy)

15:25 - 17:00

Honorary

Chair: Renato PADOVANI (ICTP, Italy), Peter KUESS (Department of Radiation Oncology, Medical University Vienna, Austria)

15:25 **AI in medicine 1h0'**
Speaker: Andreas DEKKER (Maastricht University Medical Center and Maastricht Clinic, Netherlands)

16:30 **Coffee Break 30'**

17:00 - 18:35

Radiotherapy I

Chair: Dushko LUKARSKI (University Clinic for Radiotherapy and Oncology, Skopje, North Macedonia), Marco ESPOSITO (ICTP, Italy)

- 17:00 **Challenges and developments in small field dosimetry 25'**
Speaker: Bozidar CASAR (Institute of Oncology Ljubljana, Slovenia)
- 17:25 **Multiple Energy MLC DLG verification and TPS data comparison, a study on Varian Clinac iX and Varian TrueBeam with Millenium MLC 120 10'**
Speaker: Nandor Attila JUHASZ KOLLAR (Jósa András County Hospital, Nyíregyháza, Hungary)
- 17:35 **Geant4 Based Simulation of The Gammapodtm System 10'**
Speaker: Maria Isabel SUBIA POTOSI (University of Trieste, Physics Department, Italy)
- 17:45 **Dosimetry analysis of different planning techniques of whole breast radiotherapy 10'**
Speaker: Suzana DOVIJARSKI STANKIN (Oncology Institute of Vojvodina, Serbia)
- 17:55 **Development and validation of a robust dataset using commercial TPS, radiochromic film and 2D diode matrix for deep learning in transit dosimetry 10'**
Speaker: Carlotta MOZZI (University of Florence – INFN Florence -Italy)
- 18:05 **Evaluating the impact of Diffusion Weighted Imaging for Gross Tumor Volume delineation in cervical carcinoma patients 10'**
Speaker: Lukas ZIMMERMANN (Medical University of Vienna, Department of Radiation Oncology, Austria)
- 18:15 **Evaluation of an almost-autonomous dosimetric workflow for the management of laryngeal cancer in radiotherapy 10'**
Speaker: Moritz Johannes Martin WESTERMAYER (Centre Léon Bérard Department of Radiotherapy, Lyon, France)
- 18:25 **Dosimetry and tracking accuracy evaluation of lung carcinoma treated with RADIXACT® TREATMENT DELIVERY SYSTEM and Synchrony Real-Time Delivery Adaptation using Dynamic Thorax Phantom 008A and CIRS motion platform 10'**
Speaker: Ivona ZLATKOVA (Emicenter Naples, Italy)

Friday, 23 May 2025

08:45 - 10:45

Research – diagnostic

Chair: Luca BROMBAL (University of Trieste), Manca PODVRATNIK (Institute of Occupational Safety Center for Physical Measurements Laboratory for Dosimetry, Ljubljana, Slovenia)

- 08:45 **Spectral μ CT with a photon-counting detector for quantitative ex-vivo osteoarticular imaging 25'**
Speaker: Paolo CARDARELLI (INFN Ferrara, Italy)
- 09:10 **CT imaging through combined source- and detector-generated spectral separation 10'**
Speaker: Stevan VRBAŠKI (University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Serbia)
- 09:20 **Evaluation of a New Multi-Energy QA Phantom for Spectral CT: Optimizing Diagnostic Imaging with Virtual Monochromatic Imaging and Metal Artifact Reduction 10'**
Speaker: Michèle-Louise REGNER (Department of Medical Physics and Radiation) and Lilian ABOU ASSALI (THM and IMPS, Germany)
- 09:30 **Beam Quality Assessment: Evaluating Aluminum Purity's Effect 10'**
Speaker: Sara MOHAMMADI (Kaiser Permanente Southern California, Los Angeles, CA)
- 09:40 **The LARAMED project at the INFN-LNL: Direct cyclotron-based production of medical radionuclides 10'**
Speaker: Liliana MOU (INFN, Laboratori Nazionali di Legnaro, Padova, Italy)
- 09:50 **The ISOLPHARM collaboration 10'**
Speaker: Aurora LESO (Ferrara University, Italy)
- 10:00 **Monte Carlo simulation of particle transport emitted during 123I decay: application in single-photon emission computed tomography 10'**
Speaker: Laura NAD (Medical Physics and Radiation Protection Department, University Hospital Rijeka, Croatia)
- 10:15 **Coffee Break 30'**

10:45 - 12:10

Radiology

Chair: Slaven JURKOVIĆ (Clinical Hospital Center Rijeka, Croatia) Paola BREGANT (Maggiore Hospital Cancer Center Trieste, Italy)

- 10:45 **Breast dosimetry for contrast enhanced mammography and tomosynthesis 25'**
Speaker: Renata LONGO (Department of Physics, University of Trieste and INFN Trieste, Italy)
- 11:10 **Impact of CT image data characterization on the absorbed dose calculation 10'**
Speaker: Đeni SMILOVIĆ RADOJČIĆ (Medical Physics and Radiation Protection Department, University Hospital Rijeka, Rijeka, Croatia)
- 11:20 **Evaluation of HyperSight Cone-Beam CT for Adaptive Radiotherapy: A Comparison with Conventional CT and Previous Detector Generations 10'**
Speaker: Christian OBWEGS (Graz University of Technology, Austria)

- 11:30 **Acceptance testing and initial performance evaluation of the ARTIS Pheno C-arm system at Cattinara Hospital, Italy 10'**
Speaker: Sara SAVATOVIĆ (Department of Physics and Astronomy "Galileo Galilei", University of Padua, Italy)
- 11:40 **Update of Italian diagnostic reference levels in interventional radiology 10'**
Speaker: Monica CAVALLARI (Fondazione Irccs policlinico San Matteo Pavia, Italy)
- 11:50 **Breast Density Patterns and their Relationship with Breast Cancer among a Large Cohort of Ghanaian Women 10'**
Speaker: Caroline Kachana PWAMANG (University of Ghana, School of Nuclear and Allied Sciences, Medical Physics Department, Accra, Ghana)
- 12:00 **Automated VBQ determination from T1-weighted lumbar spine MRI data using a hybrid CNN-Transformer neural network 10'**
Speaker: Kristian STOJSIC (University Hospital Rijeka, Medical Physics and Radiation Protection Department, Rijeka, Croatia)

12:10 - 14:30

EFOMP Prize

Chair: Slaven JURKOVIĆ (Clinical Hospital Center Rijeka, Croatia) Paola BREGANT (Maggiore Hospital Cancer Center Trieste, Italy)

- 12:10 **Inside EFOMP 20'**
Speaker: Efi KOUTSOUELI (EFOMP President, Hygeia Hospital, Greece)
- 12:30 **Encyclopaedia of Medical Physics - Second Edition 30'**
Speaker: Slavik TABAKOV (King's College London, UK & IUPESM)
- 13:00 **Lunch Break 1h30'**

14:30 - 17:00

Nuclear medicine

Petra TOMSE (University Medical Centre Department of Nuclear Medicine, Ljubljana, Slovenia), Jelena SAMAC (University of Novi Sad Department for Physics, Serbia)

- 14:30 **Advancing molecular imaging with long axial field of view PET/CT 25'**
Speaker: Lidia STRIGARI (IRCCS Azienda Ospedaliero-Universitaria di Bologna Department of Medical Physics, Italy)
- 14:55 **Positron emission tomography imaging using quantum correlations of annihilation gamma-ray photons with single-layer Compton polarimeters 10'**
Speaker: Ana Marija KOZULJEVIC (University of Zagreb Faculty of Science, Croatia)
- 15:05 **Optimization of a quantitative SPECT/CT reconstruction protocol: phantom measurements and preliminary clinical evaluation. 10'**
Speaker: Maria Rosa FORNASIER (Medical Physics Department, ASUGI (University Hospital), Trieste, Italy)
- 15:15 **The Defect Perfusion Index: A New Descriptor for the Characterization of Myocardial Perfusion Imaging Systems 10'**
Speaker: Dea DUNDARA DEBELJUH (Medical Physics and Radiation Protection Department, University Hospital Rijeka, Croatia)
- 15:25 **Evaluation of Monte-Carlo-based Iterative SPECT Reconstruction: anthropomorphic phantom study 10'**
Speaker: Ivan PRIBANIĆ (Medical Physics and Radiation Protection Department, University Hospital Rijeka, Croatia)
- 15:35 **Monte Carlo analysis of dose deposition by alpha emitters in Targeted Radionuclide Therapy 10'**
Speaker: Lidia PALENCIANO CASTRO (Department of Atomic, Molecular and Nuclear Physics, University of Granada, Spain)
- 15:45 **Dosimetry from a Series of Whole-Body Planar Images and One SPECT/CT in Patients Undergoing Radionuclide Therapy using ¹⁷⁷Lu- labelled Radiopharmaceuticals 10'**
Speaker: Ursa BEGUS (University Medical Centre Ljubljana, Division of Nuclear Medicine, Slovenia)
- 15:55 **Challenges in introducing LUTATHERA® to clinical practice 10'**
Speaker: Luka JENSTERLE (University Medical Centre Ljubljana, Division of Nuclear Medicine, Slovenia)
- 16:05 **Optimizing Kidney Dosimetry Workflow in ¹⁷⁷Lu-DOTATATE Therapy Through Single 10'**
Speaker: Mario LIUZZO (Ospedale Santa Maria della Misericordia di Udine, Italy)
- 16:15 **Coffee Break 45'**

17:00 - 19:01

Radiotherapy 2

Chair: Csilla PESZNYAK (National Institute of Oncology, Centre of Radiotherapy, Budapest, Hungary), Milana VEZIROVIC (Oncology Institute of Vojvodina, Serbia)

- 17:00 **Workflows and Patient information systems in a particle therapy center 25'**
Speaker: Piotr ANDRZEJEWSKI (Medical University Vienna, AKH Vienna, Department of Radiooncology, Austria)
- 17:25 **Workflow and Planning Techniques for Stereotactic Ion Beam Therapy in Treating Cardiac Arrhythmias 10'**
Speaker: Ariadna CHERIT HERNANDEZ (Karl Landsteiner Private University for Health Sciences and MedAustron, Ion Beam, Austria)
- 17:35 **Comparison of DLG values obtained with five different measurement setups 10'**
Speaker: Andrea ANDROCKI (Oncology Institute Vojvodina, Serbia)
- 17:45 **Impact of knowledge-based treatment planning on adaptive radiotherapy for prostate cancer 10'**
Speaker: Tamás PÓCZA (National Institute of Oncology, Centre of Radiotherapy, Budapest, Hungary)
- 17:55 **Evaluation of Patient-Specific Quality Assurance Software Mobius3D and VeriQA in Comparison to the Eclipse Treatment Planning System 10'**
Speaker: Thomas Georg BONÉ (University Clinic for Radiation Therapy and Radiooncology, Graz, Austria)
- 18:05 **Comparative Dosimetric Analysis of Varian Halcyon and TrueBeam Platforms for Rectum and Inguinal**

- Irradiation 10'**
Speaker: Una POPOVIĆ (Oncology Institute Vojvodina, Serbia)
- 18:15 **Metal implants, gas pockets, and intra-venous contrast – should automatic CT-ED conversion be trusted? 10'**
Speaker: Primož PETERLIN (Institute of Oncology Ljubljana, Slovenia)
- 18:25 **Measurement of PDDs for the Xstrahl 200 orthovoltage therapy machine using the PTW Advanced Markus chamber 10'**
Speaker: Attila SARVARI (Institute of Oncology Ljubljana, Slovenia)
- 18:35 **Intercomparison of calibration factor of ionizing chambers in clinical practise 10'**
Speaker: Veljko PETROVIC (University Clinical Center Niš, Serbia)

Saturday, 24 May 2025

08:45 - 11:00

Research

Chair: Marco ESPOSITO (ICTP, Italy), Tamás PÓCZA (National Institute of Oncology, Centre of Radiotherapy, Budapest, Hungary)

- 08:45 **EURADOS survey on IGRT practices in European radiotherapy clinics 25'**
Speaker: Milana VEZIROVIC (Oncology Institute of Vojvodina, Serbia)
- 09:10 **Oscillatory Interactions and Coupling Functions in Medicine 25'**
Speaker: Tomislav STANKOVSKI (Skopje University, Macedonia)
- 09:35 **Monitoring of Indoor Air Quality to Prevent diffusion of Infection Diseases and improve Occupants' Safeguards 10'**
Speaker: Benedetta SANTORO (Department of Physics, University of Trieste, Italy)
- 09:45 **Readout conditions of lithium fluorite detectors after ultrahigh dose rate irradiation 10'**
Speaker: Aleksandra JUNG (AGH University of Krakow, Faculty of Physics and Applied Computer Sciences, Krakow Poland)
- 09:55 **Calculation of electron mass stopping power in the range 0.01–1000 MeV in different human tissues 10'**
Speaker: Katarina BITO (University Clinical Center Niš, Serbia)
- 10:05 **Ionoacoustic Dosimetry: Computational Simulations for Acoustic Detection of Proton and FLASH Electron Beams 10'**
Speaker: Alessandro Michele FERRARA (Department of Physics and Astronomy "Galileo Galilei", University of Padua, Italy)
- 10:15 **Collimated Carbon ion beams for preclinical in-vivo research 10'**
Speaker: Lorenz WOLF (Division of Medical Physics, Department of Radiation Oncology, Medical University of Vienna, Austria)
- 10:25 **In Vivo Dosimetry with GDCA in Particle Therapy: Variations in Secondary Photon Radiation Across Ion Species 10'**
Speaker: Tiago BETTIO (Joaquim Chaves Saude, Faro, Portugal)
- 10:35 **Coffee Break 25'**

11:00 - 13:00

Radiation Protection

Chair: Uwe WOLFF (Medical University Vienna, Austria), Mara SEVERGNINI (University Hospital of Trieste, Italy)

- 11:05 **Towards Safe, Optimized and Personalized Radiology and Radiotherapy procedures for pregnant patients 25'**
Speaker: Zeljka KNEZEVIC MEDIJA (Ruđer Bošković Institute Radiation Chemistry and Dosimetry Laboratory Zagreb, Croatia)
- 11:30 **Radiation protection challenges in adaptive therapy 25'**
Speaker: Csilla PESZNYAK (National Institute of Oncology, Centre of Radiotherapy, Budapest, Hungary)
- 11:55 **Estimation of fetal dose during head and neck radiotherapy: Comparing IMRT and VMAT techniques for iX and Halcyon radiation units 10'**
Speaker: Elena GOLABOSKA (City General Hospital 8th September, Skopje, Macedonia,)
- 12:05 **SECURE project – Recommendations for minimization of radiation exposure in the isotope chain exposure in the isotope chain 10'**
Speaker: Petra TOMSE (University Medical Centre Ljubljana, Slovenia)
- 12:15 **Radiation Exposure of Interventional Pain Physicians 10'**
Speaker: Jelena SAMAC (Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Serbia)
- 12:25 **Experiences with microcontroller supported DAP measurements 10'**
Speaker: Csenge FORGÁCS (University of Debrecen, Faculty of Science and Technology, Institute of Physics, Hungary)
- 12:40 **Prize Conclusion 20'**

Chair: Efsthathia KOUTSOUELI (EFOMP), Mara SEVERGNINI (University Hospital of Trieste, Italy), Uwe WOLFF (Medical University Vienna, Austria)

GO TO SCIENTIFIC CALENDAR

CT imaging through combined source- and detector-generated spectral separation

Stevan Vrbaški^{1,2,3}, Adriano Contillo², and Renata Longo^{2,3}

¹ *University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Hajduk Veljkova 1-3, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia*

² *Elettra-Sincrotrone Trieste S.C.p.A, 34149 Basovizza Trieste, Italy*

³ *Department of Physics, University of Trieste, Via Valerio 2, 34127 Trieste, Italy*

Spectral computed tomography (CT) is utilized in clinical imaging to obtain virtual monochromatic images, tissue density, and effective atomic number maps [1]. Two spectral channels are just as effective as multiple spectral channels for these tasks, with the quality primarily dependent on the spectral separation of the independent channels [2]. Clinical spectral CT scanners achieve spectral separation using either dual-energy spectra or spectral detectors, such as dual-layer or photon-counting detectors.

This work has developed an approach to test the impact of spectral separation on relevant clinical tasks using the combined contribution of source-generated and detector-generated spectral separation in CT imaging. The setup was made using synchrotron radiation at SYRMEP beamline at Elettra Synchrotrone Trieste, where the polychromatic synchrotron X-ray source is spectrally shaped using a foil made of pure silver. The spectral separation on the detector side was obtained using a two-threshold photon-counting detector.

Preliminary results show that this method can obtain quantitatively correct virtual monochromatic images of tissue-equivalent inserts and estimate their density and effective atomic number. The results were validated using CT images acquired with a synchrotron beam filtered by a double-crystal monochromator (true monochromatic images) and ground truth data. The experimental setup is given in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Comparison of conventional, monochromatic imaging approach and beam-splitting technique introduced in this paper.

[1] M. H. Albrecht, T. J. Vogl, *Radiology*, **2**, 293, (2019).

[2] S. Vrbaški, R. Longo, and A. Contillo. *SPIE*, 12031 (2022).